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Thermodynamic Studies of Cr(II), Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) Chelates of *o*-(*N*- α -furfuralideneimino) Benzene Sulphonic Acid

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A perusal of the literature^{1,2} shows that no systematic study has been made on the bivalent metal chelates of *o*-(*N*- α -furfuralideneimino) benzene sulphonic acid (HFB), hence the same was undertaken. The findings of these studies are reported in the present paper.

Experimental

Metal salt used were of BDH AnalaR quality. Furfuraldehyde and orthanilic acid (L. R.) supplied by Fluka were used. Precision pH-meter type OP : 205 No. 837 (Radelkis) equipped with a glass-calomel electrode assembly was used at 25°, 35° and 45° ($\mu=0.01, 0.05$ and $0.1M$ NaClO₄). HFB was synthesised from furfuraldehyde and orthanilic acid by the method reported earlier³. It gave satisfactory elemental analyses. The titrations were

carried out in presence and in absence of the metal ions, against carbonate free 0.01M NaOH in accordance with Calvin's extension of Bjerrum method^{4,5}.

Results and Discussion

From the titration curves it is observed that the metal-ligand curve is well separated from the ligand titration curve which suggests that liberation of proton occurs due to complexation. The pK_1 of HFB as determined by interpolation at half \bar{n} values and algebraic method⁶ was 5.95, 5.77 and 5.60 at 25°, 35° and 45°. Thus the pK values fall with rise of temperature. These values suggest that HFB is a monoprotic ligand. The metal-ligand stability constants were read from the formation curves drawn by plotting \bar{n} vs $-\log[A^-]$. The refinement was done by various computational method⁷, such as correction term, convergence formula successive approximation and interpolation at various \bar{n} values methods and their average value ($\log \beta_2$) along with their deviations from the theoretical values are summarised in Table 1. The $\log \beta_2$ values of the metal chelates are in the order Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Co(II) > Fe(II) > Mn(II) > Cr(II) which is in accordance with the Irving-William rule⁸.

The thermodynamic stability constants ($\log K^\circ$) as shown in Table 1 have been obtained by extrapolation of measured formation constants to zero ionic strength from graph between \log of stability constant vs $\sqrt{\mu}$, where μ is the ionic strength.

The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) have been evaluated using Gibbs-Helmholtz equation⁹, (Table 1). The ΔG of all the chelates have more

TABLE 1—AVERAGE STABILITY CONSTANTS, THEIR DEVIATIONS* FROM THEORETICAL VALUES AND THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF THE BIVALENT METAL CHELATES OF *o*-(*N*- α -FURFURALIDENEIMINO) BENZENE SULPHONIC ACID AT 25°, 35° AND 45°

Metal	Stability constant ($\mu=0.1M$ NaClO ₄)			$\log K^\circ$			$-\Delta G$ K cal/mole			ΔH K cal/mole 35°	ΔS cal/deg/mole at 35°	
	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°			
Cr(II)	$\log K_1$	3.68	3.75	3.78								
	$\log K_2$	2.70	2.82	2.95	7.00	7.20	7.40	9.03	9.40	10.03	15.18	80.23
	$\log \beta_2$	6.38 ± 0.02	6.57 ± 0.05	6.73 ± 0.03								
Mn(II)	$\log K_1$	3.86	3.96	4.06								
	$\log K_2$	3.02	3.24	3.47	8.25	8.60	8.70	9.49	10.26	10.94	14.09	78.89
	$\log \beta_2$	6.88 ± 0.04	7.20 ± 0.02	7.53 ± 0.01								
Fe(II)	$\log K_1$	3.96	4.05	4.15								
	$\log K_2$	3.16	3.35	3.54	8.45	8.75	9.00	9.82	10.50	11.19	12.30	74.01
	$\log \beta_2$	7.12 ± 0.03	7.40 ± 0.04	7.69 ± 0.04								
Co(II)	$\log K_1$	4.23	4.37	4.66*								
	$\log K_2$	3.45	3.63	3.81	9.05	9.35	9.70	10.59	11.45	12.32	17.13	92.76
	$\log \beta_2$	7.68 ± 0.02	8.00 ± 0.04	8.47 ± 0.02								
Ni(II)	$\log K_1$	4.41	4.51	4.61								
	$\log K_2$	3.77	4.01	4.25	9.30	9.65	9.95	11.28	12.08	12.89	14.74	87.06
	$\log \beta_2$	8.18 ± 0.05	8.52 ± 0.02	8.86 ± 0.01								
Cu(II)	$\log K_1$	4.80	4.86	4.93								
	$\log K_2$	4.19	4.35	4.57	10.00	10.20	10.50	12.28	13.08	13.81	21.67	112.7
	$\log \beta_2$	8.99 ± 0.03	9.21 ± 0.01	9.49 ± 0.04								

* Very small deviations (0.01-0.05) were observed.

negative values at 45° than at 25° or 35°. It is also observed that ΔH is positive in all cases which suggests that there exists steric strain around the metal ion in the chelates due to fused rings. The positive values of ΔS for all the chelates indicate that entropy term is favourable for their formation.

The data were analysed in terms of Harned's¹⁰ relation between $\log K^H$ and temperature $[(pK_m^H - ct^2) = -2c\theta t + (pK_m^H - c\theta^2)]$. A plot of $(pK_m^H - ct^2)$ vs t must be linear and this was found true in the present case. The values of θ° and pK_m^H for HFB were found 211° and 3.550 respectively. ΔH values as calculated from Harned's equation were found 7.914, 7.794 and 7.681 at 25°, 35° and 45° respectively.

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Separation and Determination of Zirconium with N-Benzoyl-*o*-Tolyl Hydroxylamine

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N-BENZOYL-*O*-TOLYL hydroxylamine which was used for the precipitation and determination of niobium and tantalum by Majumdar and Pal¹ has later been used as a reagent in gravimetric and spectrophotometric determination of a variety of metals²⁻³.

Experimental

Reagent :

N-benzoyl-*o*-tolyl hydroxylamine was prepared by the procedure given by Pal⁴. The product was recrystallised from ethanol.

Standard Solution :

A standard solution of zirconium was prepared from Johnson & Mathey 'Specpure' zirconium oxychloride. The solution of zirconium was standardised gravimetrically as oxide by cupferron⁵ and N-benzoyl phenyl hydroxylamine⁶⁻⁷.

An Elico Model L 1-10 pH-meter was used for all pH measurements.

Procedure :

An aliquot of standard zirconium solution was diluted to 100 ml, pH was adjusted between 0.4-2.2 with dilute ammonia or mineral acid and the solution warmed. The reagent in ethanol and water mixture (1 : 1) was then added to the solution very slowly with thorough stirring after each addition, when a milky white precipitate appeared, which was digested for 20-25 minutes on the boiling water bath. The solution was then cooled to room temperature and filtered through a Whatman No. 42 filter paper, washed with 0.1% reagent solution and ignited to oxide in a platinum crucible.

pH effect :

The precipitate of zirconium was found to be quantitative between pH 0.4 to 2.2; at higher pH zirconium precipitate assumed colloidal form and at higher acid concentrations the precipitate dissolved on warming. The determination of zirconium by direct weighing was not possible since the complex was contaminated with the reagent.

Separation of foreign ions :

Solution containing known amounts of different foreign ions with zirconium were mixed with a 5% (w/v) tartaric acid solution. The amount of tartaric acid was 10-15 times the total ions. Addition of reagent (20 times the amount of zirconium) and the adjustment of pH were made according to the general procedure. The ions Ca⁺²(100 mg), Mg⁺²(100 mg), Ba⁺²(100 mg), Sr⁺²(100 mg), Be⁺²(50 mg), Al⁺³(100 mg), Ni⁺²(80 mg), Co⁺²(100 mg), Cu⁺²(100 mg), Zn⁺²(100 mg), Cd⁺²(100 mg), As⁺³(100 mg), Sn⁺²(80 mg), Hg⁺²(80 mg), UO₂⁺²(60 mg), Th⁺⁴(60 mg), Mn⁺²(100 mg), Cr⁺³(100 mg), Bi⁺³(100 mg), Ce⁺³(60 mg), Br⁻(50 mg), I⁻(50 mg) and BO₃⁻³(50 mg) did not interfere. Only Ti(IV), V(V), Ce(IV), Fe(III), Mo(IV), WO₄⁻², Nb⁺⁵, Ta⁺⁵ and Hf(IV) interfered. To remove their interfering effect iron was masked by thioglycolic acid;